

Synthesis and Physico-chemical Studies of Some Binuclear Mixed Carboxylates of Copper(II)

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Anhydrous copper(II) acetate undergoes substitution reactions with higher carboxylic acids refluxing in toluene, yielding soluble copper(II) carboxylates with general formula $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{OOCR})_n$ (where $\text{R} = \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}$, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}$ and $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}$, and $n=1$ or 2). These complexes on recrystallisation from benzene-alcohol mixtures form alcoholate complexes with the formulae, $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_3)(\text{OOCR})\text{R}'\text{OH}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCR})_2 \cdot \text{R}'\text{OH}$ (where $\text{R}' = \text{Me}$, Et and Pr^1). Elemental analyses, infrared and electronic spectra magnetic measurements and ebullioscopic molecular weight determination of all the above complexes indicate their dimeric nature with carboxylate groups acting as bridging ligands.

THE chemistry of copper(II) carboxylates has been one of the most widely investigated topics in the field of metal carboxylates in view of their interesting magnetic and structural properties arising from possible superexchange metal-metal interactions¹⁻³. A survey of the literature revealed⁴ that while an extensive amount of work has been carried out on the addition complexes of copper(II) carboxylates, almost no work has been done on their substitution reactions. It was, therefore, considered of interest to investigate the substitution reactions of copper(II) acetate with higher carboxylic acids. It has been found that these reactions are quite facile and yield mixed carboxylates, $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_3)(\text{OOCR})$ as well as anhydrous dicarboxylates, $\text{Cu}(\text{OOCR})_2$, and both crystallise out with an adduct alcohol molecule from benzene alcohol mixtures. Various physico-chemical studies have been carried out to throw light on the structure of all these derivatives.

Experimental

All the reactions were carried out under anhydrous conditions and glass apparatus with standard joints was used. The carboxylic acids were purified by distillation. Toluene was dried over sodium. Copper acetate was made anhydrous by refluxing its hydrated form with acetic anhydride followed by drying *in vacuo*.

Physico-chemical studies were made as described earlier⁵. Copper was estimated iodometrically with sodium thiosulphate and acetic acid, with standard sodium hydroxide solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. Alcohols were estimated by the oxidimetric method⁶.

Reactions of copper acetate with higher carboxylic acids To weighed amounts of copper acetate

suspended in toluene were added carboxylic acids in the required proportions and the reaction mixtures were refluxed for 4-6 h. As the liberated acetic acid was removed azeotropically (106°) with toluene the products dissolved in the solvent. The products were then recrystallised from benzene-alcohol (R'OH) mixture (4:1) and finally, the alcoholate complexes of mixed as well as dicarboxylate derivatives were obtained after removing the volatile solvents from the crystalline mass under vacuum at room temperature. The products on heating under vacuum (120/1 mm) lost the alcohol of addition, yielding coloured crystalline solids. Detailed experimental results are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

Substitution reactions of anhydrous copper(II) acetate have been carried out with higher carboxylic (myristic, palmitic, stearic and behenic) acids in different stoichiometric ratios refluxing in toluene

where $\text{R} = \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}$, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}$ and $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}$, and $n=1$ or 2

These reactions may also be considered as transacylation reactions. The use of toluene as a solvent makes it easier to remove acetic acid liberated during the course of reactions azeotropically and made it possible to carry out the above reactions in 1:1 as well as in 1:2 molar ratios. The reactions are found to be facile and their progress was followed by estimating the liberated acetic acid content of the azeotrope collected during

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TABLE 1—REACTION PRODUCTS OF COPPER(II) ACETATE AND CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

Sl. no.	Reactants g	Molar ratio	Product and state	Acetic acid in azeotrope (g) Found/(Calcd.)	Copper (%) Found/(Calcd.)	Mol. Wt.* Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ cm^{-1}
1.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{12}H_{22}O_4$ 1.0 1.2	1 : 1	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21})$ green solid	0.82 (0.89)	18.05 (18.10)	723 (850)	1.42	15880
2.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{10}H_{18}O_4$ 0.9 2.9	1 : 2	$Cu(OOC C_{10}H_{17})_2$ green solid	0.60 (0.61)	12.19 (12.26)	1013 (518)	1.43	15827
3.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{12}H_{22}O_4$ 2.9 4.1	1 : 1	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21})$ green solid	0.96 (0.98)	16.78 (16.81)	729 (878)	1.48	15840
4.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{12}H_{22}O_4$ 1.8 4.5	1 : 2	$Cu(OOC C_{12}H_{21})_2$ green solid	0.99 (1.06)	10.95 (11.06)	1109 (574)	1.46	15810
5.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{11}H_{20}O_4$ 2.1 3.3	1 : 1	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{11}H_{19})$ greenish blue solid	0.68 (0.70)	15.56 (15.65)	791 (406)	1.38	15827
6.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{11}H_{20}O_4$ 1.4 4.4	1 : 2	$Cu(OOC C_{11}H_{19})_2$ green solid	0.90 (0.98)	10.02 (10.08)	1162 (630)	1.37	15285
7.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{10}H_{18}O_4$ 0.5 0.9	1 : 1	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{10}H_{17})$ greenish blue solid	0.16 (0.17)	18.58 (18.75)	901 (462)	1.40	15840
8.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2 + C_{12}H_{22}O_4$ 0.7 2.6	1 : 2	$Cu(OOC C_{12}H_{21})_2$ green solid	0.41 (0.46)	8.51 (8.55)	1458 (749)	1.42	15190

In chloroform.

TABLE 2—ALCOHOLATE ADDUCTS OF CARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II)

Sl. no.	Compound	Solvent*	Product and state	Analysis (%): Found/(Calcd.)		Mol. Wt.* Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ cm^{-1}
				Copper	Alcohol			
1.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21})$	MeOH	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21}) \cdot MeOH$ light green solid	16.46 (16.68)	—	780 (322)	1.43	15400
2.	$Cu(OOC C_{10}H_{17})_2$	MeOH	$Cu(OOC C_{10}H_{17})_2 \cdot MeOH$ light green solid	11.44 (11.54)	—	1142 (560)	1.45	15810
3.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21})$	EtOH	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21}) \cdot EtOH$ light green solid	14.91 (14.98)	10.77 (10.86)	861 (424)	1.46	15255
4.	$Cu(OOC C_{12}H_{21})_2$	Pr ¹ OH	$Cu(OOC C_{12}H_{21})_2 \cdot Pr^1OH$ greenish blue solid	10.21 (10.02)	9.88 (9.48)	1809 (684)	1.43	15220
5.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{11}H_{19})$	Pr ¹ OH	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{11}H_{19}) \cdot Pr^1OH$ greenish blue solid	13.54 (13.63)	12.81 (12.89)	—	1.40	15170
6.	$Cu(OOC C_{10}H_{17})_2$	EtOH	$Cu(OOC C_{10}H_{17})_2 \cdot EtOH$ light green solid	9.46 (9.89)	6.72 (6.81)	—	1.40	15100
7.	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21})$	MeOH	$Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOC C_{12}H_{21}) \cdot MeOH$ bluish green solid	12.77 (12.86)	—	—	1.42	15360
8.	$Cu(OOC C_{12}H_{21})_2$	MeOH	$Cu(OOC C_{12}H_{21})_2 \cdot MeOH$ light green solid	8.41 (8.20)	—	—	1.45	15080

* Plus benzene.

continuous fractionation. Mono- and di-substituted products have been obtained in quantitative yields.

All the derivatives are coloured, non-volatile solids and are soluble in benzene and toluene, but they are insoluble in alcohols; these are, therefore, precipitated by adding alcohol to a benzene solution. On heating again the precipitated products dissolved and on cooling, coloured crystals were obtained with the formula $Cu(OOCCH_3)_{2-n}(OOCR)_n \cdot R'OH$ ($R' = Me, Et$ and Pr^1 , and $n=1$ or 2). The adduct-molecule of alcohol appears to be lost at $\sim 120^\circ/1$ mm pressure leaving the mixed as well as dicarboxylate derivatives of copper without any adduct-alcohol molecule. It may be emphasised that transacylation method appears to be particularly suited for the synthesis of mixed carboxylate derivatives of copper(II) which can not be so easily synthesised by any other route. The solubility of mixed soap derivatives, $Cu(OOCCH_3)(OOCR)$, shows that these products are not equimolar mixtures of

$Cu(OOCCH_3)_2$ and $Cu(OOCR)_2$, as the former is insoluble in benzene or toluene.

Infrared spectra: Infrared spectra (KBr) of all the complexes were recorded in the range $400-4000$ cm^{-1} . In these spectra, the characteristic ~ 1710 ($C=O$ stretching), ~ 3300 (OH stretching) and ~ 935 cm^{-1} (OH deformation) vibrations of free carboxylic acids⁷ were found completely missing from their respective regions. The spectra, however, exhibited strong bands at ~ 1590 and ~ 1460 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to antisymmetric and symmetric C—O stretching vibrations (ν_s and ν_a)⁸; the observed shifts towards higher side in these bands from 1578 and 1414 cm^{-1} , respectively in the spectrum of acetate ion⁹ may be attributed to coordinated state of the carboxylate moiety. Out of the two possible

modes¹⁰ of coordination and

the latter appears to be more

probable on the basis of the higher value of ν_{OH} ; this is corroborated by the appearance of ν_{OH} at the same position (1590 cm^{-1}) in the spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{OOCCH}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]_n$ in which bridging type of coordination has been established by X-ray studies. In alcoholate complexes, the OH stretching vibration is found to be present at $\sim 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the lowering in its value indicates the coordinating nature of the alcohol molecules⁹. Some other vibrations below 700 cm^{-1} may be ascribed to Cu-O stretching vibrations.

Electronic spectra and magnetic moments: Electronic spectra (nujol/benzene) of all the carboxylate derivatives have been recorded in the range $12500\text{--}25000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and no marked difference could be observed in their spectra. The spectra exhibit a very broad antisymmetric band around $15200 \pm 200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, characteristic of a d^9 ion in a tetragonal ligand field. This band may be assigned¹² to ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and its broadness is expected for the CuO_6 chromophore because of the Jahn-Teller distortion in tetragonal field.

Magnetic moment of all these derivatives have been measured at room temperature and the results indicate that all the complexes show a magnetic moment in the range 1.38-1.49 B.M. The lower value of the magnetic moment in these complexes as compared to a spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. for a d^9 system is due to Cu-Cu interaction^{13,14}. A slightly higher value of the magnetic moment of their alcoholate complexes may be indicative of the expected lesser Cu-Cu interaction due to the copper atoms being coordinated to the alcohol molecules.

Molecular weights and probable structure: Molecular weights of the above carboxylate derivatives

have been determined ebullioscopically in refluxing chloroform and the values obtained (Table 1 and 2) show that copper mixed carboxylates, dicarboxylates as well as their alcohol adducts are dimeric in nature. Both the magnetic and spectral studies indicate that copper atoms in all the above derivatives are situated in a tetragonal environment. Although some direct experimental evidence is essential before a final view of structure can be arrived at, the dimeric structures suggested for copper acetate and its monohydrate^{10,16} appear to be the most plausible ones for the above carboxylate derivatives as well as their mono-alcoholate complexes, respectively.

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